

Black-Box AI Agents (B²A²) inside Pandora's Box

Jackie Jianhong Shen*

*Managing Director
Head of Algos and E-Trading Risks and Analytics
Cantor Fitzgerald, New York, USA*

May 24, 2026

Contents

1	Eden of Full Autonomy	1
2	B²A²-1: Cost Snowballing by Hidden Memories	2
3	B²A²-2: Backdoor Internet Search and Utilization	3
4	B²A²-3: Jungle of Complex Internal Data	4
5	B²A²-4: Should We Fully Trust AI's Coding?	6
6	B²A²-5: Role of Compliance AI Agents (CAA)	7
7	Conclusion	9
8	Acknowledgment and Disclaimer	10

Abstract

Once the box is opened, B²A²'s will baffle most existing control frameworks within modern corporate environments, and potentially spark another pandemic. They must be designed with a minimum set of requirements on transparency and controls. The discussion herein mostly focuses on investment banks, but the principles or frameworks are universal.

1 Eden of Full Autonomy

A B²A² refers to an AI agent that delivers solutions directly to a user's voice or typed requests, without intermediate human-in-the-loop (HITL) checkpoints, nor displaying (on the front end) or logging (on the back end) key information about task planning, tools utilization, data source reliance, memory management, or any built-in controls, etc.

The dream of reaching full autonomy, which partially emulates how God created Adam and Eva, has been live for millennia and now made ever more possible. But just as how our genesis couple were sadly banished from the Garden of Eden, full autonomy may pay a heavy price.

The river of free will must flow along a well fortified river bank. Otherwise, it could flood the land of prosperity and ruthlessly sink modern societies.

*Email: jhshen@alum.mit.edu; URL: <https://alum.mit.edu/www/jhshen>; Video: [Youtube Paper Companion](#)

2 B²A²-1: Cost Snowballing by Hidden Memories

Figure 1: Lack of transparency and control on mounting token cost by B²A²'s.

In the cost-conscious environment of modern corporations, the top concern about B²A²'s, whether purchased from vendors or internally developed, is how they handle *memory management*.

This is nothing new to most software developers. In the earlier days of programming, memory management was key to successfully tackling large-scale complex tasks. A developer had to meticulously allocate, release, or recycle the memories for working variables or objects.

One could be unforgivably done if she or he had failed to explain the mechanism neatly in a job interview. Only years later, most languages like Java and Python started to manage them automatically behind the scene, including smart garbage collection for example.

For AI agents, memory management elevates to a new plateau. In some sense, it becomes vividly relatable even to our dear grandmas, since it literally means to manage the “memory” - which sort of apple-pie recipes one has specifically asked about 10 minutes ago, or if you are a trader, on which industrial sectors you have kept on bugging an agent with intriguing investment ideas.

Keeping long memory is always beneficial to AI agents. For instance, a stressful trader could easily get agitated if an agent replies with: “Sorry, what do you mean by the \$456MM order in the morning,” when the trader wants to revisit how that order has been faring by 3:30pm before the market close. To meet such needs, an AI agent may retain the memory of an entire day, week or even longer, to more genuinely emulate the mind of a competitive human agent. They probably have no second options in order to serve demanding humans, who already start to treat them like junior team members.

But the cost of long memories mounts up. It could well blow up if B²A²'s are offered to a large number of employees in a sizable corporation, say 1,000 or 10,000. From 9am to 5pm, and from Monday to Friday, long memories could turn to a roaring river of tokens and quickly engulf a firm's treasury department.

To most investment banks whose client commission fees are typically at the minute level of basis points (bps, one cent out of 100 dollars), constant snowballing of token charges may eat up a significant chunk of profits.

This is a typical nightmare of cost created by B²A²'s, especially when

- they do not explicitly offer its users some control buttons or capability of memory management, including e.g., periodic condensation of raw memories or a total flush of older memories, and
- they do not display on the frontend dashboard the individual or firm-wide total costs in real time.

Even when they do offer these functionalities, some residual pains still remain on how to properly take actions by individual employees, AI engineers, or the middle office. We believe the ultimate solution is the following.

Solution to the Current Fee Model

The current token-fee model may work for individual or retail LLM subscribers but will suffer a heavy headwind when applied to large corporations. It must switch to a prepaid monthly or annual lump-sum fee model, possibly via a multi-tier fee schedule.

3 B²A²-2: Backdoor Internet Search and Utilization

Figure 2: Lack of transparency on backdoor internet search and exact usage.

One common misunderstanding among the general populace is that LLMs need to be constantly retrained in order to keep abreast of the real-time state of the world. It is certainly not necessary. LLMs only handle “how to speak or extract properly.” It is the internet search engines behind the scene that fetch “what to say about the real-time world.”

As a result, internet search becomes vital for AI agents to keep track of the real-time world, and be able to address any inquiries regarding more recent or live events.

For instance, one can ask about an investment-advisor AI agent: “Based on the 2026 Q1 earning report of stock ZVZZT just released a minute ago, advise how I should adjust my position of +100,000 shares of ZVZZT and the targeted holding period.” The agent may call an internal tool called:

```
rebalance(ticker, shares, stock_analysis),
```

where the `JSON` or dictionary summary (key-value pairs) of `stock_analysis` is prepared by the LLM “brain” of the agent after searching the earning report just released a minute ago.

Use cases like this well justify why AI agents must be allowed to access the internet for fresh or most relevant information. But as long as this backdoor is open, so is the gate to information demons - rumors, misinformation, or any content that is inappropriate morally, socially, culturally, or commercially, etc.

For most B²A²'s, there is a lack of guardianship on what to access and how to properly utilize the fetched information. There is a common lack of disclosure.

- (i) When a B²A² answers that “The current price of KPKKQ is \$432.10,” we are actually not informed on whether it arrives at this price by (a) using the firm’s internal tool called `get_current_market_price(ticker)`, which subscribes to expensive but high-quality real-time market data, or (b) after scraping free financial websites like Yahoo!Finance or CNBC with some expected delay in pricing.

- (ii) When a B²A² answers that “The most recent stock rating for ZVZZT by Barclays is ‘Overweight,’” we are similarly not informed on whether it is based on the February release about two months ago or the most recent one just published this morning.
- (iii) If the B²A² is client-facing, it may inadvertently respond with some offensive languages, such as discriminatory comments against age, gender, or racial profiles, etc. This is the contamination or brainwashing by bad contents on the internet.

The following measures could enhance the much-needed transparency of AI agents in terms of disclosing their backdoor search activities and actual information utilization.

Transparency on Internet Search and Utilization

- There is a frontend side panel or backend logger file that allows a user to check out in detail (if needed) which information sources an answer is based upon, e.g., via internet search, a predesigned set of tools accessing internal data, or both.
- This logger file can be saved in a local user directory or a firm’s servers. It may also serve a more critical corporate purpose - providing an audit trail if anything goes awry, either on trading, investment, or client services, etc.
- Whenever an AI agent provides a final answer, it should also list the website addresses from which the final answer has been fully or partially derived. At a minimum, it should display a message banner of “Based on Internal Data,” “Based on External Internet,” or in any more itemized manner.
- For client-facing AI agents, there must be a *Compliance AI Agent* (CAA) (or a team of them) devoted to various compliance and risk-control checks before the final answers can be safely released to clients. The CAA’s are the critical guardrails and will be covered in Section 6.

4 B²A²-3: Jungle of Complex Internal Data

Figure 3: Extremely risky granting unguided and unrestricted database access to B²A²’s.

AI agents or agent teams rely on many internal “tools,” which are often structured codes or programs that generate analytics from various internal data sources.

Databases have been with financial institutions for decades, long before the current AI wave started to gather attention. Throughout the years, they have typically turned more and more

complex since people come and go with different styles, and tables or files are also frequently being created, modified, or re-organized.

For example, the field names of a data table could become quite obscure, e.g., `ord_size` intended for order size but unclear whether in terms of dollar notional or number of shares, or `trans_time` intended for the time when a transaction of an order occurs but without specifics on which action it actually refers to, i.e., submitted, acknowledged, revised, rejected, filled, etc. Data values could also be a bit arbitrary sometime, e.g., 1 for “buy” and 0 for “sell”, or the other way around.

The jungle of data imposes no big challenges to professional engineers who have got used to the wrestling after years of learning. Now the question becomes: should we entrust an AI agent being a “professional” or an “amateur?”

Suppose that at 3:00pm, a trader asks an AI agent: “Please list all orders I have placed during today’s volatile period between 2pm and 2:30pm,” and the agent subsequently utilizes the database connection tool provided, and writes a query to fetch all orders between 14:00:00 and 14:30:00, and finally renders the orders beautifully on the trader’s dashboard. What could possibly go wrong for such a relatively simple task? No one tells the AI agent that the default timestamp column is in *UTC - Coordinated Universal Time*. Thus the New York trader has been mistakenly presented with all orders during 10:00:00 and 10:30:00 in local time (assuming during the summer Daylight Saving Time when New York is 4 hours behind).

Nuances of a similar nature could present significant challenges to “innocent” AI agents. Traditional databases (e.g., SQL, KDB) were born long before the LLM era. They do have conventional schemas that define the typing information for each field or column, e.g.,

```
allow_NYSE_close_auction_4pm | BOOLEAN | DEFAULT TRUE.
```

But there have been no incentives to store more descriptive information about each field until now when LLM-based AI agents begin to fetch data on their own.

Coding languages like Python rely on documentation strings (*a.k.a.*, docstrings) to inform users or other coders about the basic purposes, and inputs and outputs of a function, method or class. Docstrings are now perfect for AI agents, since they do need to read and “digest” before they can correctly invoke a function or method! Traditional databases are not so lucky.

Imagine in the above example that somewhere in the meta description of the trading database, there is a docstring like this: “`order_place_time` is in UTC. Please always remember to convert to your local trading time.” With this built-in “prompt,” it is unlikely that a more recent and evolved LLM “brain” could miss the UTC-to-Local-Time conversion.

Therefore, one should not just leave alone a B²A² to access the internal databases and hope that it can figure out the meaning of every single field on its own.

Supplying the Missed Database Docstrings

For each AI agent that is granted the access to an internal database, there should be created sufficiently detailed docstrings for all the relevant tables, to express the meaning and background of each field. They could be formatted as JSON key-value pairs, e.g.,

```
{
  order_place_time: "type:time; time when an order is placed; in UTC; should
                    be converted to local trading time zone for traders",
  side:             "value: 0 or 1; for buy or sell; buy=1, sell=0",
  ...
}
```

Without being supplied with such ground truth, an AI agent could not possibly outperform any new joiners in terms of developing accurate and meaningful data analytics.

So far we have emphasized how to help AI agents better navigate internal databases. There is, however, a hidden ticking bomb piggybacked on an AI agent’s access to a database. Such an agent could inadvertently alter a production database that is critical for trading or investment! For example, it could submit risky queries like:

```
DROP TABLE live_trading_table; or
DELETE FROM live_trading_table where id=007.
```

Therefore, one should exercise due diligence when leaving a database open to AI agents.

Restricting Database Accessing Rights by AI Agents

- Never directly copy and paste your existing database credentials for an AI agent or agentic team.
- Instead, create restricted accessing accounts specifically for AI agents. In particular, never grant table dropping or deletion rights.
- For row insertion or deletion operations, supply AI agents with preconfigured wrapper functions or tools, with some built-in safety checks or controls.

Otherwise, it could blow up to a total nightmare, e.g., suddenly halting a production process (like suspension of active trading) or violating regulatory rules on retaining critical data.

5 B²A²-4: Should We Fully Trust AI’s Coding?

The answer is No. And there is no “but.”

Figure 4: SDLC is the golden standard for software developments, esp. on complex projects. It is risky allowing B²A²’s to run their on-the-fly codes in sophisticated production environments.

Ever since software development took on central stage, there has been a gradual convergence towards the unified standards of “Software Development Life Cycle” (SDLC). Key principles include:

- **“4-Eye” Check.** After completion of coding, there should be at least one more teammate to independently review and validate it.
- **Unit Tests.** To add or modify any functions or methods, there must be a set of companion tests that verify the desirable behavior of these new or updated units, including inputs, outputs, and processing of regular and edge cases.

- **Regression Tests.** For any changes of functions, methods or design patterns, one must demonstrate that they are compatible with existing frameworks and codes, and facilitate system-wide smooth integration in order to deliver the expected functionalities.

For decades, SDLC principles like these even apply to senior and experienced software developers. Now the question is: can AI agents be spared from these well-established guardrails?

AI agents appear to code “better” than even experienced software developers. Unfortunately, this is nothing more than an illusion, and partially (and possibly unintentionally) hyped up by some AI startup companies.

In many localized use cases, the risk is indeed contained when AI agents utilize their on-the-fly codes, e.g., aggregating some numerical columns from a database, figuring out the 36th number in the Fibonacci sequence, or implementing Black-Scholes’ option pricing formula. These are often standardized tasks with a huge body of existing literature in the internet.

But for other more complex and trickier applications, one should stay highly vigilant, esp. for those involving an existing production environment, a complex web of interdependency on other existing software components, or demanding new and unconventional design patterns.

Illusion about AI Agents’ Coding Superiority

- It is true that AI agents or coding-specialized LLMs can put together code snippets much faster than humans, and virtually for any programming languages.
- When supplied as version 0.0 for human developers, these codes often result in unprecedented efficiency and productivity for software development.
- But we should be extremely cautious to allow B²A²’s to develop codes on the fly and immediately utilize them in production, especially when embedded in a sophisticated software environment. Lack of carefully designed unit/regression and integration tests could result in erroneous or even disastrous consequences.
- For complex coding, no saying rings truer than: “The devil is in the details.” Examples of such details include subtle temporal ordering of events, correct multi-threading, impacts from modifying global variables or settings shared across many processes, and the complex web of logic orchestrating multiple components, etc.
- Being able to self-correct errors and get the codes running through is one thing. Producing accurate and relevant analytical results could be a totally different one. Erroneous results lead to wrong business decisions or client actions.

At a minimum, any on-the-fly code snippets created and utilized by an AI agent must be properly saved or logged for debugging and auditing purposes.

For most tasks, human developers can utilize the draft versions created by AI or agents off line, and then supply the fully tested and matured versions as designated tools *back* to AI agents. *This coding cycle of AI-Human-AI fortifies robustness and sanity!* It can address most coding needs of AI agents while substantially improving transparency.

6 B²A² -5: Role of Compliance AI Agents (CAA)

One closely related area from which we can draw deep inspiration is *Algorithmic Trading*.

Historically, after a systematic switch from traditional manual/voice trading to automated trading, it did not take long for major investment banks like Goldman to converge to the right philosophy of risk controls: “automated trading requires *automated* controls.” From fat-finger controls to client credit-limit checks, and from detailed exchange rules to restricted trading lists, each control should be automated right before orders are pushed out to the street.

Figure 5: CAA’s will become critical in the architecture of agentic workflows.

With unprecedented autonomy (in decision making) and automation (in action taking), a similar approach could be followed for the risk controls of AI agents. That is, we should rely upon a combination of automated controls using conventional software, as well as AI agents specifically dedicated to control checks on other AI agents.

We call these agents *the Compliance AI Agents* (CAA), a concept first coined and discussed in the author’s another recent article - *“Generative AI on Wall Street - Opportunities and Risk Controls”*.

The notion of CAA itself is critical. It is true that control statements can already be easily injected into agents in the form of “instructions,” e.g.,

- “You are a customer agent, and you *never reveal the confidential account* information of another customer B when you are chatting with customer A,” or
- “As a trader, you place *bona fide* orders on behalf of the firm out of legitimate business objectives such as market making or hedging. But you *never trade names on the Firm’s Restricted Trading List*.”

However, with the innate stochastic way how LLMs and agents react to instructions and also sometimes how memories fade, there is always a non-negligible chance of violation.

A CAA also accepts such verbal instructions, but is devoted exclusively to controls. It does not require growing memories since each instance should be independently handled for compliance checks. For example, how the previous 10 orders have been accepted or rejected does not influence how the 11th new order should be censored by a CAA.

More importantly, a CAA can be equipped with numerous conventional software tools for compliance or control checks. These tools are often more structured and have been matured over the years in order to deliver precise regulatory (e.g., for US: [SEC](#), [FINRA](#), [CFTC](#), [Federal Reserve](#), etc.) or compliance controls.

Based on the specific task areas that an AI agent or agentic team works on, CAA’s can at least make contributions in the following ways.

How CAA's Can Improve Risk Controls and Transparency of B²A²'s

- When accessing databases, reject risky database operations like `DROP TABLE live_trading_orders`.
- When interacting directly with clients or customers, reject any final outputs that are inappropriate, discriminatory or offensive, or breach data privacy.
- If the outputs of an AI agent or agentic team are part of the parameter set defining a production action (e.g., trading in national exchanges), a CAA can ensure that these outputs go through the established flow of controls and validations, and reject them if there are any breaches.
- CAA's can provide the most valuable interface between AI agents and humans. They can post real-time control messages on the dedicated windows or dashboards for human stakeholders to review or respond. They can also relay real-time human instructions back to the agents. This practice genuinely honors the principle of *Humans in the Loop* (HITL).
- For each production action of an AI agent or agentic team, the control flow of a CAA or CAA manager should be properly logged for auditing or regulatory purposes. Such documentation should be retained for some minimum periods, in case there are any adverse impacts caused by the agent's actions and a need to revisit.

Finally, we should also stay vigilant should there be any signs hinting the collusion between AI agents and their CAA's. Sound design and architecture should be able to reduce such likelihood.

7 Conclusion

When the box is ready to be opened, we must make sure that the AI agents or agentic teams inside are sufficiently transparent. Black-box AI agents (B²A²) are incompatible with modern business models, regulatory requirements, or compliance and risk control needs.

Transparency will Become a Hard Constraint

Developers of agents or agentic workflows must deliver such transparency via

- (a) frontend user dashboards so that a typical corporate or consumer user can understand what is going on behind the curtain, what are the data sources leading to the outputs, and what are their accumulative token charges, etc, and
- (b) backend loggers or more formal documentation so that engineers or middle-office controllers can look into what is actually going on inside the agentic black boxes, and revisit or reconstruct the workflow when investigating adverse scenarios.

The author projects that in the coming few years, such transparency features are not only just for marketing agentic products and services, but will also become hard requirements by most institutions, regulators, and compliance and risk functions.

A key notion we have promoted in this article is the *Compliance AI Agents* (CAA's). Together with other conventional software controls, they will become the central force for implementing and delivering regulatory, compliance or generic risk controls.

We conclude this article by emphasizing that AI agents or agentic workflows are after all still software components. Therefore, they must be subject to all the established control procedures

in modern corporate environments.

AI Agents Should Not Be Spared from Existing Requirements

- (c) **Documentation Requirement.** There should be a comprehensive inventory system that documents each production use case of AI agents or agentic workflows, including though not limited to, intended usage and scope, list of API's or pre-coded tools, database usage, LLM vendors and versions, system diagrams, and controls, etc.
- (c) **Pre-deployment Validation Requirement.** There should be a designated team in the second line of defense that is exclusively devoted to the validation and testing of AI agents or agentic workflows before their production releases. It may or may not reside within the **Model Risk Management** (MRM) department.
- (c) **Post-deployment Monitoring Requirement.** There should be a centralized monitoring and tracking system that is exclusively devoted to post-deployment monitoring and incidents tracking. It may or may not coincide with a firm's **Operational Risk Management** (OpRisk) system.

8 Acknowledgment and Disclaimer

The author would like to informally dedicate this article to Prof. Andrew Karolyi, Dean of Cornell University SC Johnson College of Business. I was lucky to serve as a panelist in a recent panel discussion led by Andrew. He shared both his faith in “*AI for Finance*” and also his scholastic approach of always staying *constructively critical*. That has deeply inspired the theme and tone of the current work.

Disclaimer and Disclosure.

- (A) The current article could be considered as a sequel to our earlier paper “*Generative AI on Wall Street - Opportunities and Risk Controls.*”
- (B) The views herein are exclusively the author's, and have not been endorsed by any of the current or previous employers (e.g., Cantor Fitzgerald or Goldman Sachs).
- (C) All images have been graciously generated by Google's Nano Banana for free.
- (D) For this rapidly evolving subject, the contents could soon become obsolete.

Finally, we also have to painfully accept the irreversible new reality that once published in any archive sites, the contents will immediately feed into AI and AI can produce a much better piece in whatever sense.

But as already pacified in the author's preceding paper mentioned in (A), the joy of composition stays and cannot be copied. This unique type of joy is best expressed by [Einstein](#):

“The object of all science, whether natural science or psychology, is to co-ordinate our experiences and to bring them into a logical system.”

It is certainly true also to the fields of AI, Finance, etc. Out of all opinions rampantly permeating this era of social media and podcasts, we herein seek some slightly more coherent and logical comprehension of what is still under supersonic evolution.